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THE RELEVANCE OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN, PRIORITIES IN THE TOURISM SECTOR

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Abstract. The article provides the analysis of various methods the visit of international tourists to Uzbekistan and what type of tours they are interested in.

Key words. Inbound tourism, World Bank indicators, tourist gender, age of tourists, tourists occupation, traveling type, type of tours, travel seasons.

Introduction

International tourism, number of arrivals in Uzbekistan was reported at 6749000 in 2019, according to the World Bank collection of development indicators, compiled from officially recognized sources.

Uzbekistan - International tourism, number of arrivals - actual values, historical data, forecasts and projections were sourced from the World Bank on November of 2023. International inbound tourists (overnight visitors) are the number of tourists who travel to a country other than that in which they have their usual residence, but outside their usual environment, for a period not exceeding 12 months and whose main purpose in visiting is other than an activity remunerated from within the country visited. When data on number of tourists are not available, the number of visitors, which includes tourists, same-day visitors, cruise passengers, and crew members, is shown instead. Sources and collection methods for arrivals differ across countries.

In some cases data are from border statistics (police, immigration, and the like) and supplemented by border surveys. In other cases data are from tourism accommodation establishments. For some countries number of arrivals is limited to arrivals by air and for others to arrivals staying in hotels. Some countries include arrivals of nationals residing abroad while others do not. Caution should thus be used in comparing arrivals across countries. The data on inbound tourists refer to the number of arrivals, not to the number of people traveling. Thus a person who makes several trips to a country during a given period is counted each time as a new arrival. This page includes a historical data

chart, news and forecasts for International tourism; number of arrivals in Uzbekistan.

Uzbek government aims to reach two million visitors in the near future. During the visit from officials from UNWTO and the Secretary-General, Taleb Rifai, the government of Uzbekistan officially announced that it is aiming to reach two million visitors a year within next five years. Currently, with around 800,000 international tourists a year, this is more than doubling the number of visitors within five years. Rarely does the Uzbek government publicize such ambitious plans; only if it has a strong intention of achieving them.

Figure 1. International tourism, number of arrivals in Uzbekistan.

Table 1 shows the gender of the respondents. The table shows that most of the respondents are male (53% or 263 respondents), while female respondents are (42 % or 209), and no response 5% or 25.

Table 1

Tourist gender

Respondents	Quantity	%
Male	263	53%
Female	209	42%
Not responded	25	5%
Total	497	100%

Another important point is the age of tourists. According to the statistical information received from NC "Uzbek Tourism", the average age of tourists who

visit Uzbekistan is between 46-65 years which is 56% of total tourists. Only 10% of tourists are with young ages and 24% are between 36-45 years. (Figure-2)

Figure-2. Age of tourists who visit Uzbekistan

The Table 2 shows that almost respondents are professionals (40 % or 199) which includes of teachers, office workers, 33% or 164 of them are retired, and only 17 % or 84 are students, and other includes respondents 10% or 50.

Table-2
Tourist occupation

Respondents	Quantity	%
Professionals	199	40%
Retired	164	33%
Students	84	17%
Others	50	10%
Total	497	100%

The survey results confirmed that, the most tourists to Uzbekistan travel with inclusive tour packages. This means all travel, hotels, and most meals, are selected in advance by a tour operator. The tour operators sell their packages to tour retailers in the home countries, in particular Germany, France, Japan, Netherlands, Britain and USA. While there are few tourists who make repeat visits to Uzbekistan, the others will purchase another trip from the same tour retailer. Table 4.2.4 shows that's 278 (56%) of respondents they inclusive by tour packages, 114 (23%) of them traveling alone, and 104 (21%) of respondents are traveling with family or with friends.

Table 3
Traveling type

Respondents	Quantity of respondents	%
Package tours	278	56%

Alone	114	23%
Family members/friends	104	21%
Total	497	100%

Also, it is important to know which type of tours are popular among tourists, in order to have a picture in which direction to develop marketing strategy for improving Uzbek tourism and increasing world awareness about the country. The following statistical data was accessed by surveying travel agencies during research. Travel agencies were asked to list types of tours starting from the most popular one to the least popular. The results received were very interesting. Travel agencies consider Historical-tourism (410) as the most perspective type of tourism, then eco-tourism, cultural, sport, and historical and other types of tourism (Figure 3). The data shown below is drawn for peak season time of Tourism.

As National Company “Uzbek Tourism” states, there are three types of travel seasons:

Peak season: April May, September, and October

Non season: January, February, and December

Mid-season: March, June, July, August, and November.

Sometimes special tours to Samarkand and Bukhara are organized during nonseason periods if the occasions of some events.

The sample roughly matches descriptions and general impressions of the existing Uzbekistan tourism market. Almost all business and holiday visitors to Uzbekistan pass through or stay in Tashkent. Most travelers stay about two weeks in the country. For most visitors, this is a “once in a lifetime” trip and they do not expect to return. Most spent about US\$3500 on the trip, per person. Almost all tourists, and a significant share of business visitors, go to the key tourist sites in Samarkand and Bukhara.

Figure-4.Type of tours in Uzbekistan

The sample roughly matches descriptions and general impressions of the existing Uzbekistan tourism market. Almost all business and holiday visitors to Uzbekistan pass through or stay in Tashkent. Most travelers stay about two weeks in the country. For most visitors, this is a “once in a lifetime” trip and they do not expect to return. Most spent about US\$3500 on the trip, per person. Almost all tourists, and a significant share of business visitors, go to the key tourist sites in Samarkand and Bukhara. Khiva is smaller and more remote, yet it still attracts about three quarters of holiday visitors and more than one in ten business visitors. It would seem that many “business” visitors also take the opportunity to see the key tourist sites. Most tourists liked Uzbekistan and 88% said they would recommend a visit to a friend.

Uzbekistan is seen as an exotic destination for the experienced tourist, who has probably already visited many other countries. Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva are seen as world- class historic sites, there are local handicrafts especially in Bukhara, and there is some “nature” tourism in the desert and mountains around Fergana valley. However, in comparison with say India or Turkey the country lacks attractions such as beaches, interesting food or art galleries. It is therefore unattractive to families or young adults, who may wish to combine a variety of “serious” sightseeing with relaxation. The survey results confirmed our view that there is substantial growth potential for tourism to Uzbekistan, subject mostly to the general impression of security in the region. There are now direct flights from most European and Asian capital cities. Although hotel and

restaurant facilities are not, in general, luxurious, they are mostly to an acceptable international standard and there is ample spare capacity.

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